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Seedling to seed – A novel single season cabbage seed production technology for extreme cold deserts

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Abstract: For the completion of life cycle and seed production, cabbage demands two distinct growth seasons namely vegetative and reproductive. In this paper, a new methodology christened 'seedling to seed' enabling the cabbage seed production within a single season is explained. Current season seedlings exposed to high-level vernalisation at an average temperature of 2.52°C continuously for 17 weeks at Ladakh conditions (trans-Himalayan zone, India) bolted readily and continued to produce seeds throughout the season. Seed yield (626.80 g/m²) was higher over conventional double season techniques such as 'head to seed' (511.93) and 'seed to seed' (356.39). This technique opens up the possibility of obtaining pure seeds of novel varieties within a season by artificial vernalisation techniques.

Key words: *Brassica*, cabbage, over wintering, seed production, seedling to seed, vernalisation.

Introduction

Cabbage (*Brassica oleraceae* L. var. *capitata*), known for its biennial nature holds two specific growth phases namely vegetative and reproductive (Niewhof, 1969). The former is characterized by the formation of head optimized at 15-22°C whereas the latter leads to bolting and seed production only after getting the necessary stimulus of low temperature at 4.4-10.0°C for about 60 days for head dormancy breaking (Verma and Sharma, 2000), thus demanding a minimum of two growth seasons for seed production. Vernalisation is a process of conversion of plant vegetative phase to reproductive through cold stimulus (Snyder and Hogaboam, 1980) and the requisite for all biennial vegetables including cabbage, at complete vegetative maturity is worked out (Verma and Sharma, 2000). This specificity as mentioned above makes the cabbage seed production impossible in north Indian plains, except in case of the cultivar Pusa Agathi (Anonymous, 2004). In the absence of vernalisation temperatures, cabbage plants remain vegetative even in second season. Bolting stalks, instead of producing floral buds makes vegetative growth for some time before initiation of another head (Miller, 1929), leading to perennial growth.

Prevailing seed production systems in cabbage namely seed to seed and head to seed are environment directed, the former characterized by *in situ* completion of both seasons in open field and the latter by the underground cellar storage of first

season heads during winters and are specific for mild and extreme cold conditions respectively (Frydrych, 1987).

Ladakh, at an altitude of 11,500ft above MSL in the trans-Himalayas is agriculturally unique with extreme cold arid desert conditions which includes extra ordinary size of the produce (Singh, 1995), bolting in conventionally vegetative crops (Mathew *et al.*, 2005) and spontaneous mutations (Mathew, 2007) which are often guided by low temperature, long photoperiods, high light intensity and higher level of UV-B in sunlight. A unique phenomenon of vernalisation induced seedling bolting and seed production was observed under trench greenhouse conditions in winter cabbages in Ladakh, opening a new avenue for seed production by skipping the heading stage and double seasons, christened seedling to seed method.

Material and Methods

May to September is the agricultural season in Ladakh, restricted by extreme cold and unprecedented snowfall that could wipe out an early or late crop, otherwise under protected conditions. Off-season cabbage crop (early cultivar Golden Acre) was sown in the last week of October under trench greenhouse and was transplanted inside the same during the first week of January at 50 x 50 cm spacing. The delay in transplanting was due to slow seedling growth effected by low temperatures within the

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Table 1. Comparison on seed to seed, head to seed and seedling to seed methods of seed production in cabbage under cold desert conditions of Ladakh

Parameter	Seed to seed	Head to seed	Seedling to seed
1. Plant height (cm)	31.8±2.71 ^c	118.7±16.37 ^a	87.4±10.32 ^b
2. Number of flower heads	11.8±1.92 ^a	10.3±2.11 ^a	7.9±0.86 ^b
3. Per cent field establishment	87.5±6.04 ^b	90.1±4.94 ^b	100.0 ^a
4. Start of second season fresh growth	February first week	April last week	Continuous growth
5. Flower initiation	March last week	June second week	March last week
6. Completion of seed harvest	July second week	September first week	June last week
7. Seed yield/plant	128.3±12.49 ^c	184.3±18.63 ^a	156.7±13.66 ^b
8. Spacing (cm ²)	60 X 60	60 X 60	50 X 50
8. Yield/m ² (g) (considering the yield/plant, per cent establishment and spacing)	356.39±25.91 ^c	511.93±38.70 ^b	626.80±86.98 ^a
9. Seed germination (%)	> 95	> 95	> 95
10. Labour required	No extra labour	Labour intensive	No extra labour

^{a-c} means, within a row, values associated with same alphabet do not differ significantly at 0.05 level in t-test, replications - 10.

trench (Fig. 1) that was recorded using Datalogger (model WDL 1002, Weather Technologies), transferred using detachable memory module and analyzed using the software Comdrv prmpnt 1.1. For

comparative studies on existing seed production methods, first season heads stored under cellars were transplanted in open during the first week of April (head to seed) and also the *in situ* heads of last season

were protected under polytunnels during extreme winters (seed to seed). Entire experiment was laid out using Completely Randomized Design with 10 replications in Seedling to Seed, Seed to Seed and Head to Seed methodologies, each consisting of 10 plants. Quantitative data on plant height, number of flower heads, per cent seedling establishment, seed yield per plant and productivity from two years experiments were pooled together and analyzed statistically using student t-test. Significant superiority of methodologies for each quantitative character were estimated at 5 per cent level and presented using mean separation. Qualitative data on earliness in fresh growth in the second season, flowering and completion of seed harvest and labour requisite were also recorded.

Results and Discussion

In seedling to seed method, flowering was observed in the last week of March simultaneous to that in *in situ* seed to seed plants. Figure 1 shows that right from the date of germination (first week of November) till one week before bolting (first week of March); seedlings were exposed to mean weekly temperatures less than 8.26°C (ranging from -0.7 to 8.26°C with overall mean of 2.52°C, over both years), continuously for 17 weeks. It is clear that in this case, high-level vernalisation at this temperature range leads to bolting immediately after attaining

sexual maturity. In early cultivars of cabbage, sexual maturity falls at 17 weeks after germination. Also, higher temperature levels maintained within the trench had led to the completion of seed harvest two weeks in advance to biennial seed to seed method and 65 days ahead of conventional head to seed identified for extreme cold regions (Table 1). Moreover, high level seedling establishment facilitated by gap filling coupled with higher population due to lower spacing requirement effected by tall growth habit lead to highest seed yield of 626.80 g/m² compared to seed to seed (356.39 g) and conventional head to seed (511.93 g), though the per plant yield is lesser (156.7 g) compared to head to seed (184.3 g). Higher yield under head to seed method compared to seed to seed (Verma *et al.*, 1996) and its positive correlation with head size (Pathania and Negi, 1993) were supportive to previous reports. Qualitatively, fully matured seeds were equally good with respect to germination and viability, irrespective of the method of production. Apart from saving one season and high yield, this method holds the benefit of being lesser labour intensive, better purity and potential to quicken breeding cycles. Moreover, benefit-cost ratio is almost doubled because the labour charges are halved since the seed harvest is completed within single season and further, harvest after first season, transportation, storage and replanting procedures are avoided.

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